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Women and Local Political Representation in the Italian Regions

The presence of women in local political representation grew by 68.48% between 2012 and 2022.

Istat calculates the value of women and local political representation in the Italian regions. The variable represents the percentage of women elected to regional councils out of the total number of those elected. The data refers to the Italian regions in the period 2012-2022.

Ranking of the Italian regions for the value of women and local political representation in the Italian regions in 2022. Umbria is in first place for the value of women in political representation with a value of 38.1, followed by Veneto with a value of 35.3 units and from Tuscany with an amount of 35.00 units. In the middle of the table are Lombardy with a value of 24.7 units, followed by Sicily with a value of 21.4 units and Liguria with a value of 19.4 units. Sardinia closes the ranking with a value of 13.3 units, followed by Valle d'Aosta with 11.4 units and Basilicata with an amount of 4.8 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change of women in political representation in the Italian regions between 2012 and 2022. Molise is in first place for the value of women in political representation in the Italian regions between 2012 and 2022 with an equal value at +766.67% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 3.3 units up to a value of 28.6 units. Veneto follows with a variation equal to an amount of 426.87% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 6.7 units up to a value of 35.3 units. Puglia is in third place with a value of 218.6% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 4.3 units up to a value of 13.7 units. In the middle of the table are Lazio with a value of 68.82% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 18.6 units up to a value of 31.4 units. Emilia Romagna follows with a value of 50.94% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 21.2 units up to a value of 32 units. Basilicata with a variation equal to an amount of +45.45% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 3.3 units up to a value of 4.8 units. Valle d'Aosta closes the ranking with a value of -20.28% corresponding to a reduction from an amount of 14.3 units to a value of 11.4. Piedmont follows with a value of -32.62% corresponding to a variation from 23.3 to 15.7 units. Campania in last place with a value of -33.19% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 23.5 units up to a value of 15.7 units. Overall, the value of women in local representation in the Italian regions grew by 68.48% between 2012 and 2022.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Sardinia, Abruzzo, Puglia, Valle d'Aosta, Liguria, Friuli Venezia Giulia;
- Cluster 2: Lazio, Tuscany, Trentino Alto Adige, Emilia Romagna, Umbria, Marche, Lombardy, Veneto, Campania, Piedmont, Molise, Sicily.

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Considering the average value of the clusters we can note the following ordering: $C2 > C1$. However, looking at the composition of the clusters it is possible to verify that both Cluster 2 and Cluster 1 are essentially made up of regions that are absolutely heterogeneous from a geographical, economic and social point of view. Therefore, in order to obtain a more effective clustering in identifying groups between regions, we set a value of $k=3$. We therefore obtain the following cluster structure:

- Cluster 1: Sardinia, Abruzzo, Puglia
- Cluster 2: Emilia Romagna, Lazio, Tuscany, Trentino Alto Adige, Piedmont, Campania, Umbria;
- Cluster 3: Sicily, Lombardy, Molise, Liguria, Marche, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Veneto, Valle d'Aosta.

From the point of view of the average of the clusters we can identify the following ordering: $C2 > C1 > C3$. We can see that the heterogeneity of the clusters persists even going from a value of $k=2$ up to a value of $k=3$. Therefore, we must conclude that the fact that there are certain regions that have a high presence of women in local representation cannot be connected to geographical factors, or per capita income. This is a fact that instead concerns the social and political dynamics within the regions. For example, if we consider the cluster with the highest value of women in local representation, i.e. the regions of cluster 2, we can note regions of Northern, Central Italy and Southern Italy. The regions of cluster 2 are also very heterogeneous from the point of view of per capita income and from the point of view of human capital endowment. Therefore, it is not possible to offer exogenous reasons for the ability of certain regions to excel in increasing women in local political representation.

Italian macro-regions. The participation of women in local representation grew in all Italian macro-regions between 2012 and 2022. Specifically, this value grew in the North-East by a value of 107.75%, in Southern Italy by a value of 102.53%, in the Central Italy for an amount of 92.4%, in the North for an amount of 68.12%, in the South for an amount of 65.35%, in the Islands for an amount of 31.11%, in North-West for an amount of 30.2%.

Conclusions. The presence of women elected in the institutions of regional political representation grew in all Italian macro-regions between 2012 and 2022. However, not in all Italian regions. In fact, this value has decreased in Valle d'Aosta, Piedmont and Campania. However, despite this growth in absolute and percentage terms we can note that this value remains very small. If we consider 2022 for example, we can note that on average in the Italian regions, women elected to the regional council were 22 out of 100. The region with the maximum number of women elected to the regional council is Umbria with a value of 38%. It therefore follows that we are very far from having a value that can even approach 50%. That is, women are structurally underrepresented in regional councils in all Italian regions. To increase the number of women elected and ensure that there is true equality, it may be necessary to introduce new rules that consider the election of the regional council valid only when an equal number of men and women are reached among the elected councillors.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

Macro-Regioni	2012	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Nord-est	12,9	26,8	13,9	107,75
Sud	7,9	16	8,1	102,53
Centro	17,1	32,9	15,8	92,4
Nord	13,8	23,2	9,4	68,12
Mezzogiorno	10,1	16,7	6,6	65,35
Isole	13,5	17,7	4,2	31,11
Nord-ovest	14,9	19,4	4,5	30,2

Rank	Regione	2012	2022	Var Ass	Var Per	Rank	Regione	2012	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
1	Molise	3,3	28,6	25,3	766,67	11	Basilicata	3,3	4,8	1,5	45,45
2	Veneto	6,7	35,3	28,6	426,87	12	Abruzzo	11,1	16,1	5	45,05
3	Puglia	4,3	13,7	9,4	218,6	13	Trentino-Alto Adige	18,6	25,7	7,1	38,17
4	Lombardia	8,8	24,7	15,9	180,68	14	Sardegna	10	13,3	3,3	33
5	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	5,1	14,3	9,2	180,39	15	Liguria	15	19,4	4,4	29,33
6	Umbria	16,1	38,1	22	136,65	16	Sicilia	16,7	21,4	4,7	28,14
7	Toscana	16,4	35	18,6	113,41	17	Valle d'Aosta	14,3	11,4	-2,9	-20,28
8	Marche	16,3	29	12,7	77,91	18	Piemonte	23,3	15,7	-7,6	-32,62
9	Lazio	18,6	31,4	12,8	68,82	19	Campania	23,5	15,7	-7,8	-33,19
10	Emilia-Romagna	21,2	32	10,8	50,94						

Rank	Regione	2022	Rank	Regione	2022
1	<i>Umbria</i>	38,1	11	<i>Liguria</i>	19,4
2	<i>Veneto</i>	35,3	12	<i>Calabria</i>	19,4
3	<i>Toscana</i>	35,0	13	<i>Abruzzo</i>	16,1
4	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	32,0	14	<i>Piemonte</i>	15,7
5	<i>Lazio</i>	31,4	15	<i>Campania</i>	15,7
6	<i>Marche</i>	29,0	16	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	14,3
7	<i>Molise</i>	28,6	17	<i>Puglia</i>	13,7
8	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	25,7	18	<i>Sardegna</i>	13,3
9	<i>Lombardia</i>	24,7	19	<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	11,4
10	<i>Sicilia</i>	21,4	20	<i>Basilicata</i>	4,8

